

Research Data Management

Storage, Backup & Recovery Strategy

Leibniz Institute of
Ecological Urban and
Regional Development

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Abstract

Research Data Management (RDM) provides the strategies, guidelines, and measures to manage research data. Like a mosaic, RDM requires multiple pieces of multidisciplinary knowledge and competencies, and Data Management Planning (DMP) is the operational tool to handle research data. Among the different aspects, DMP cares to protect the research data asset by defining the action required to safely store, backup, and recover lost data in the worst-case scenario. This document aims to briefly describe the storage, backup and recovery strategy adopted at the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER).

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Introduction

Research data is the most valuable asset alongside the scientific and analytic competencies of the researchers. Therefore, data preservation, storage and backups are crucial components of the Research Data Management (RDM) strategy and should follow best practices to prevent data-storage disasters (Perkel, 2019)¹. Funding agencies to assure the liability of publicly funded research demand the adoption of Data Management Plans (DMPs), which explicitly require describing the strategies and requirements of the data storage and backup systems. Backup features range in terms of best-practice, e.g. the 3-2-1 rule (Three copies, two type media storage and one copy Off-Site), Media Storage adopted (cloud solutions, hard drives, magnetic tapes, etc.), backup strategy (Mirroring backup, Full backup, Incremental backup, etc.), level of automation (manual or automatic schedule), frequency (Sub-daily, Daily, weekly, etc.), latency (synchronous vs asynchronous) and data recovery reaction time (near real-time, minutes, hours). Furthermore, research projects might vary dramatically in data requirements among the same research department. Hence, it is fundamental to assess each project specifically to define the best solution based on the dataset's nature, volume, or data protection requirements. Ultimately, RDM is a mosaic of multidisciplinary knowledge and competencies. Hence, this document aims to establish a knowledge block describing the data storage, backup and recovery solutions adopted at the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER).

Backup and Recovery System

At the IOER, alongside the primary server used directly by the researchers, the backup system follows a 3-3-2 Rule (Figure 1): Three copies of the research data, with three different types of Storage Media and two offline copies (on two different storage types) in a different location. Figure 2 shows the scheme that summarizes the storage, backup and recovery system adopted at IOER. The User File-Server allows the users to quick recovery any data accidentally lost by using the built-in salvage feature without the intervention of the IT services. Three different backup systems run asynchronously on a daily schedule. Two

¹ Perkel, J. M. (2019). 11 ways to avert a data-storage disaster. *Nature*, 568(7751), 131–133.

backup servers (Backup 1 and Backup 2) perform daily mirroring backups and provide quick response recovery actions. The Backup 3 at initialization run a Full Backup and after that runs incremental backups. Finally, an extra special full backup is available upon user request.

Figure 1. 3 – 3 – 2 Backup Rule, Data stored with 3 copies in 3 different Storage Media with two offline copies.

Figure 2. The research data backup and recovery system scheme.